

Experiments on the Synthesis of ψ -Opianic Acid. Part I.

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ψ -Opianic acid (IV) was first obtained by Perkin by the hydrolysis of berberal by means of dilute sulphuric acid (Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1890, 57, 1064). Its importance is apparent when it is remembered that the constitution assigned to berberal and berberine by Perkin and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 319) is based in the first instance on that of ψ -opianic acid.

The first attempt to synthesise ψ -opianic acid was made by Solomon by the oxidation of ψ -meconine (*Ber.*, 1887, 20, 888) when he discovered the striking fact that whilst meconine was oxidized quantitatively to opianic acid, ψ -meconine was unaffected under similar conditions.

The next important attempt on record is that of Perkin and Stoye, (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 3173) when they tried to obtain ψ -opianic acid from isovanillic acid by an application of the Tiemann-Reimer reaction.

It was found however that the only product obtained by the action of chloroform and caustic potash was 5-hydroxy-4-methoxy-2-aldehydo-benzoic acid.

The last attempt on record was made by Edwards, Perkin and Stoye (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 196) when they tried to obtain it by the oxidation of ψ -meconine on lines similar to those of Solomon.

The first scheme that has now been tried will be clear from the following formulæ-sketch:

6-Nitro-2: 3-dimethoxy-benzaldehyde (I) was obtained by the separation of the nitration product obtained by the nitration of *o*-veratraldehyde (Perkin, Roberts, and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 2389; Perkin, Robinson, and Stoyke, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 2355). During the course of these experiments, the interesting observation was made that, contrary to the statements of the previous investigators, the nitration product was obviously a mixture and that it could be separated by a very careful series of fractional crystallisations, into the two components, 6-nitro-2: 3-dimethoxy-benzaldehyde and 5-nitro-2: 3-dimethoxy-benzaldehyde.

As a result of a number of comparative experiments, it was found that the reduction of 6-nitro-2: 3-dimethoxybenzaldehyde to the corresponding amino compound (II) is best effected by means of ferrous sulphate and ammonia under the conditions described. The hydrochloride, the phenylhydrazone and the benzoyl derivative of the 6-amino-2: 3-dimethoxy-benzaldehyde (II), have been prepared. The amino compound (II) itself is very unstable and on boiling with solvents like alcohol passes into a curious condensation product, which is a yellow crystalline base, m.p. 235° and may have the following constitution (V).

The next step in the synthesis consisted in the displacement of the amino group by the nitrile group by an application of the usual Sandmeyer's reaction. Though a large number of experiments were tried, the conversion of 6-amino-2: 3-dimethoxy benzaldehyde (II) into 6-cyan-2: 3-dimethoxy benzaldehyde could not be effected and therefore this simple route to the synthesis of ψ -opianic acid had to be abandoned. In this connection it is interesting to observe that there does not seem to be on record the synthesis of a single *o*-cyanaldehyde of the aromatic series. An attempt by Rilliet and Kreitman to prepare 6-cyan-piperonal from 6-amino-piperonal was unsuccessful (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1921, 4, 596).

The second series of attempts centred on the oxidation of ψ -mecocine. It seemed curious that it should be found impossible to oxidize an alcohol to the aldehyde, and therefore the problem of

oxidation of ψ -meconine and salts of ψ -meconinic acid was reinvestigated. For the oxidation the action of the following oxidizing agents was investigated under a variety of different conditions: (i) manganese dioxide and dilute sulphuric acid; (ii) dichromate and sulphuric acid; (iii) lead dioxide and dilute sulphuric acid; (iv) alkaline hydrogen peroxide; (v) potassium permanganate in acetone solution; (vi) alkaline permanganate. Unfortunately, however, ψ -meconine is so resistant to oxidation that no trace of the aldehydo-acid could be isolated, the ψ -meconine being either recovered unchanged, or in extreme cases completely destroyed.

In view of the failure of the attempts at direct oxidation not only of ψ -meconine, but also of 3:4-methylene-dioxy-phthalide (Perkin and Trikojus, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 2931) and of 4:5-methylene-dioxy-phthalide (Stevens and Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 131, 2791) to aldehydo-acids it was thought desirable to devise methods by which the conversion of the phthalide to aldehydo-acid could be easily accomplished. The next two schemes for the synthesis of ψ -opianic acid were developed with this idea in view

The first of these devices would be clear from the following scheme:—

The idea was to introduce a halogen atom in the side chain of the phthalide and then to hydrolyse the product to the corresponding aldehydo-acid. In the case of ordinary phthalide the introduction of a halogen atom in the side chain can be readily effected (Racine, *Annalen*, 1887, 239, 79; Gabriel, *Ber.*, 1916, 49, 1912) and the halogenated product is smoothly hydrolysed to *o*-phthalaldehydic acid.

Bromination of ψ -meconine was tried at temperatures varying from 140° to 180° in bright sunlight. Unfortunately in every case, as it was feared at the outset, part of the bromine enters the nucleus and part of it goes to the side chain. The hydrolysed product consists mainly of an aldehydo-acid containing bromine in the nucleus, which probably has the constitution (VI). This substance

has not yet been obtained in a pure form. Experiments are in progress for preparing its derivatives.

The next scheme that was attempted would be clear from the following formulae—

The first stage in the scheme consisted in converting ψ -meconine into ψ -meconinic ester. It is well known that the acids of the type of meconinic acid (XII) and 2-hydroxymethylbenzoic acid (XIII) are very unstable and not a single ester of this class of acids has so far been prepared. It was surprising therefore to find that ψ -meconinic

ester could be readily prepared from ψ -meconine by converting the latter into silver ψ -meconinate through the barium salt and finally treating the silver salt with methyl iodide in presence of ether. ψ -Meconinic ester is a beautifully crystalline substance, m.p. 72—3°.

The next step consisted in converting ψ -meconinic methyl ester (VII) into methyl 2-chloromethyl-3:4-dimethoxy-benzoate (VIII), but

inspite of a large number of attempts with reagents like thionyl chloride, phosphorous pentachloride, hydrochloric acid gas and hydrobromic acid, the replacement of the hydroxyl by a halogen atom could not be effected, the unstable ester being readily decomposed by these reagents back into ψ -meconine. In this connection it is of interest to note that in a somewhat similar case Wegscheider and Rusnov (*Monatsh.*, 1908, **24**, 385; *Sitzungsber.*, 1908, **112**, 217) found it impossible to convert hemipinic acid-methyl ester (XIV) into the corresponding acid chloride, hemipinic anhydride (XV) being the main product of reaction.

Attempts were next made to prepare 2-chlor- or brom-methyl-3 : 4-dimethoxybenzoic acid (XVI) from ψ -meconine by the action of phosphorous pentachloride or hydrobromic acid. In the course of these experiments it was found that ψ -meconine was unaffected by

phosphorous pentachloride at ordinary temperature or by a short treatment at 100° or even at 160° , and it was left unchanged by hydrobromic acid in glacial acetic acid under conditions under which the lactone of 6-hydroxy-methyl-homopiperonylic acid is converted into 6-brom-methyl homopiperonylic acid (Stevens, *J. Chem Soc.*, 1927, **131**, 186). This remarkable stability of ψ -meconine is hard to understand and further experiments on the action of hydrobromic acid on ψ -meconine are in progress.

The fifth scheme for the synthesis of ψ -opianic acid consisted in attempts at conversion of 2-cyan-veratric acid (XVII) into ψ -opianic acid by means of stannous chloride in presence of an

etheral solution of hydrogen chloride according to the valuable method for the conversion of nitriles into aldehydes devised by Stephen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1874).

2-Cyan-veratric acid which had first been obtained by Hoogeworff and Van Dorp (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1895, 14, 272) from hemipinic acid has now been prepared from 2-amino-veratric acid by an application of the Sandmeyer's reaction, 2-aminoveratric acid itself being obtained from vanillin by a modification of the methods of Pschorr and Sumuleneau (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 3408). The attempts to reduce 2-cyan-veratric acid (XVII) to ψ -opianic acid by Stephen's method were unsuccessful, undoubtedly largely due to steric factors as both the *ortho*-positions to the nitrile group are substituted. Attempts to reduce the ester of (XVII) were also unsuccessful.

The sixth and the final scheme that was tried would be clear from the following formulae sketch:—

The easiest way to make 6-nitro-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid (XVIII), the essential starting substance for this scheme, it would appear was to condense 6-nitro-2:3-dimethoxy-benzaldehyde with malonic acid in pyridine solution in presence of piperidine. Contrary to usual experience, it was found that by this method only a 10 % yield of 6-nitro-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid is obtained, and as the starting substance was difficult to obtain in large quantities, this method of preparation had to be abandoned. Ultimately it was found that a better method for making this acid was by the nitration of 2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid. The nitration of 2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid was first carried out by Rubenstein (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 648) who, without any adequate proof, assumed that the nitration product consisted of a mixture of

5-nitro-2 : 3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid and 6-nitro-2 : 3-dimethoxy cinnamic acid, the former preponderating. As the condition of nitration was also not definitely stated, the whole problem of nitration was reinvestigated. Nitration was carried out under a variety of different conditions with a view to obtain maximum yield of 6-nitro-2 : 3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid.

In the nitration of ordinary cinnamic acid the yield of the *ortho*-nitro-cinnamic acid increases with the increase in concentration of nitric acid (Muller, *Annalen*, 1882, 212, 128). It was therefore thought that if fuming nitric acid were used in place of ordinary nitric acid for nitration, the yield of the 6-nitro-2 : 3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid might be improved. When, however, the nitration was carried out with fuming nitric acid, the product consisted mainly of a dinitro-cinnamic acid which is of interest in view of the fact that five vicinal hydrogen atoms are substituted in this compound. The dinitro-compound is probably 5 : 6-dinitro-2 : 3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid (XXII).

The conditions which were ultimately chosen for nitration is described (p. 223). Even under these conditions the nitration product consists of only about 10 % of 6-nitro-2 : 3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid (XVIII), while the rest consisted of 5-nitro-2 : 3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid. The separation of the two nitro-compounds as described by Rubenstein (*loc. cit.*) was found to be tedious, and later on it was found that the two acids could be more readily separated if the nitration product was converted straightway into a mixture of methyl esters and the esters were then separated by a careful series of fractional crystallisation from alcohol and benzene.

6-Nitro-2 : 3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid, m. p. 220°, and its ethyl and methyl esters are described in the experimental section (p. 225). Its constitution was proved in the first place by showing its identity with 6-nitro-2 : 3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid obtained from 6-nitro-2 : 3-dimethoxy-benzaldehyde, whose constitution has already been established by Perkin, Robinson and Stoye (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 2355), by means of mixed melting points of the acid and their esters. In the second place the acid, m. p. 220°,

obtained after separation was oxidized by means of alkaline permanganate in presence of benzene to 6-nitro-2:3-dimethoxy-benzaldehyde, m. p. 110°.

6-Nitro-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid is smoothly reduced to 6-amino-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid (XIX) by means of ferrous sulphate and ammonia. The latter acid was next converted into 6-cyan-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid by an application of the usual Sandmeyer's reaction.

The next step in the scheme consisted in the oxidation of 6-cyan-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid (XX) to 6-cyan-2:3-dimethoxy-benzaldehyde (XXI). It was hoped that this oxidation would be easily effected by alkaline permanganate in presence of benzene, but so far all the experiments in this direction have been unsuccessful, the only neutral oxidation product obtained consisting of a high melting substance, whose constitution so far, owing to the small amount of the substance being available, has not been completely cleared up. The failure of this oxidation is very curious for, under similar conditions, 5-cyan-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid gives 5-cyan-2:3-dimethoxybenzaldehyde in an yield of 80% (Chakravarti and Perkin, *J. Chem., Soc.*, 1929, 135, 195), while 6-nitro-2:3-dimethoxy cinnamic acid gives 6-nitro-2:3-dimethoxy-benzaldehyde in fairly good yields (see p. 26).

It was next thought that oxidation of 6-carboxy-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid (XXIII) to ψ -opianic acid might, perhaps, be easier to accomplish. For this purpose 6-carboxy-2:3-dimethoxy cinnamic acid (XXIII) was prepared by the hydrolysis of 6-cyan-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid (XX) by means of 10% caustic soda solution.

But attempts at oxidation by means of alkaline permanganate under conditions similar to those by which Ehrlich obtained *o*-phthalaldehydic acid from *o*-carboxy-cinnamic acid (*Monatsh.*, 1889, 10, 576; *Sitzungsber.*, 1889, 98, 1594) and under other conditions were unsuccessful, an acid, m. p. 202° being obtained which differed from ψ -opianic acid in properties.

Though all the attempt to synthesise ψ -opianic acid have so far been unsuccessful, it is hoped that the synthesis of this acid would soon be accomplished in light of these fresh results.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The nitration of *o*-veratraldehyde was carried out essentially under the conditions described by Perkin, Roberts and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, **105**, 2389). The product of nitration was crystallised from methyl alcohol and then subjected to a series of careful fractional crystallisations when the heterogeneous character of the product became evident and from the more soluble fractions small quantities of 6-nitro-2:3-dimethoxy-benzaldehyde, m. p. 110°, was isolated in pure condition (1 g. from 10 g.) (Found: N, 6.7. $C_9H_9O_5N$ requires N, 6.6 per cent.). Separation on a larger scale was effected under conditions similar to those described by Perkin, Robinson and Stoye (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 2357).

For reduction of 6-nitro-2:3-dimethoxy-benzaldehyde (I) to the corresponding amino-derivative (II) the actions of the following reducing agents were investigated:—(1) ammonium sulphide on the *p*-toluidine derivative of the nitro-aldehyde; (2) sodium sulphide on the *p*-toluidine derivative under conditions similar to those recommended by Rilliet and Kreitmann (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1921, **4**, 591); (3) ferrous sulphate and sodium carbonate on the bisulphite compound of the nitro-aldehyde (compare Troger and Dunker, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1925, (ii), **111**, 208); (4) ferrous sulphate and ammonia on the bisulphite compound of the nitro-aldehyde; (5) ferrous sulphate and ammonia.

As a result of these comparative experiments it was found that the reduction is best effected by means of ferrous sulphate and ammonia under the following conditions:—

To a solution of ferrous sulphate (26 g. in 60 c. c. water) was added 6-nitro-2:3 dimethoxy-benzaldehyde (2 g.) and the mixture heated up to boiling and to the boiling mixture was added gradually concentrated ammonia (11 c. c.), and the whole shaken vigorously. The mixture was heated for a quarter of an hour more and filtered hot. The filtrate as well as the precipitate was thoroughly extracted with ether (ten times). The ethereal solution (A) was dried over sodium sulphate and the solution

saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas. The *hydrochloride* of the amine was precipitated as an almost colourless powder (1.65 g.). It was filtered, washed with dry ether and dried in a desiccator. (Found: C, 49.4 ; H, 5.5. $C_9H_{11}O_3N$, HCl requires C, 49.6 ; H, 5.5 per cent.).

In a previous experiment it was found that if the ethereal extract (A) of the amine as obtained above was concentrated down and the residue crystallised from benzene or alcohol, the amine first formed was changed into a complex condensation or polymerisation product. The substance thus obtained crystallised in yellow prisms, m.p. 235°, and was insoluble in dilute acids, whereas the crude amine obtained by removal of ether at ordinary temperatures under reduced pressure was readily soluble in dilute mineral acids. (Found: N, 8.28. $C_{18}H_{20}N_2O_5$ requires N, 8.14 ; the amine (II) requires N, 7.73 per cent.).

The benzoyl derivative.—Benzoyl chloride (1 c. c.) was added to an ethereal extract (A) of the amine (from 1 g. of the nitro-compound) and the whole kept overnight, the ether removed, and the residue was shaken up with dilute caustic soda. The whole was extracted with benzene, the extract dried over sodium sulphate, the solvent removed by distillation, and the residue was crystallised twice from alcohol. The benzoyl derivative of 6-amino-2:3-dimethoxy-benzaldehyde was thus obtained in beautiful needles, m. p. 150°. (Found: C, 67.1 ; H, 5.2. $C_{16}H_{15}O_4N$ requires C, 67.4 ; H, 5.3 per cent.).

The phenylhydrazone of 6-amino-2:3-dimethoxy-benzaldehyde was prepared by adding a slight excess phenylhydrazine (0.8 g.) to the ethereal extract (A) of the amine (from 1 g. of the nitro-compound) and allowing the whole to stand overnight, removing the ether, boiling the product for a few minutes with alcohol and finally crystallising the product from benzene. It was obtained as colourless plates, m. p. 133°.

Diazotization of the amine (II) and attempts at replacement of the amino group by nitrile.—(i) A clear diazo solution is not obtained when diazotization is carried on under usual conditions. 0.1 G. of the amine or amine hydrochloride is taken up in dilute hydrochloric acid (2 c. c.). As soon as a drop of sodium nitrite is added to this solution a red ochreous precipitate appears, which increases as more sodium nitrite is added and

the whole of the amine is precipitated as a reddish powder, insoluble in water, and soluble in alcohol from which it could not be obtained crystalline. (ii) In concentrated hydrochloric acid diazotization seems to take place and a clear solution is obtained which gives a red dye when coupled with β -naphthol in alkaline solution. When a clear diazotized solution was added to the required amount of hot potassium cuprous cyanide solution in the usual manner, not a trace of the cyanide could be isolated, either by steam-distillation of the product or extraction with benzene or chloroform. (iii) The amine hydrochloride (0.2 g.) was taken up in absolute alcohol (10 c. c.) and amyl nitrite (0.3 g.) added at 0° or at usual temperature with constant stirring till the whole went into solution. On diluting with ether, the diazo-compound separated out and was either extracted with ice-water or filtered rapidly. The solution of the diazo-compound thus obtained was treated with the required amount or excess of potassium-cuprous cyanide in the usual way, but no cyanide could be isolated. (iv) Attempts at diazotization in glacial acetic acid in presence of the required amount of hydrochloric acid and replacement by the nitrile group were also unsuccessful. The only products that were obtained were either tarry substances which were not hydrolysed to any acid, or substances which were insoluble in organic solvents.

Action of Alkaline Hydrogen peroxide on ψ -Meconine.—(i) ψ -Meconine (0.1 g.) was dissolved in 2.5 % caustic soda solution (10 c. c.) and treated with 6 % hydrogen peroxide (5 c. c.) and kept for 12 hours. No visible reaction takes place. On acidification with concentrated hydrochloric acid and allowing to stand, beautiful long needles, m.p. 123-24° separated. The precipitate was insoluble in sodium carbonate and was found to be unchanged ψ -meconine. The filtrate was extracted with ether, the solution dried and the solvent removed when very slight residue was obtained which consisted of ψ -meconine. (ii) ψ -Meconine (0.1 g.) was dissolved in 2.5 % caustic soda solution (10 c. c.) by warming and treated with 30 % hydrogen peroxide (1 c. c.) and kept for 12 hours. No visible reaction takes place. On acidification beautiful long needles gradually separated which proved on examination to be the unchanged ψ -meconine. The filtrate was extracted with ether, and ether removed when a slight non-acid residue was obtained. (iii) ψ -Meconine (0.1 g.) was dissolved in 2.5 % caustic soda solution

(10 c. c.) and treated with excess of 30 % hydrogen peroxide and the whole warmed up for about an hour. ψ -Meconine was again recovered unchanged.

Action of Potassium Dichromate and dilute Sulphuric acid on ψ -Meconine.—(i) To a boiling solution of ψ -meconine (0.2 g.) in water was gradually added a mixture of potassium dichromate (0.1 g.) sulphuric acid (1.5 c. c.) and water (4 c. c.) and warmed for 15 minutes. On allowing to cool, most of the ψ -meconine separated unchanged. (i) A solution of potassium dichromate (0.2 g.) in a mixture of sulphuric acid (1 c. c.) and water (1.5 c. c.) was added to ψ -meconine (0.1 g.), and the whole boiled for a few minutes. Most of the ψ -meconine was recovered unchanged, while part of it was oxidized away and could not be recovered.

Action of manganese dioxide and dilute sulphuric acid on ψ -Meconine.—(i) ψ -Meconine (0.3 g.) was boiled under reflux with 20% sulphuric acid (5 c.c.) and finely powdered manganese dioxide (1 g.) for three hours. The resulting solution on filtration and cooling deposited beautiful needles of unchanged ψ -meconine. The mother-liquor was extracted with ether, the ether solution dried and the ether evaporated off when a slight non-acid residue was left. (ii) Heating was continued for six hours under the above conditions. Most of the ψ -meconine was again recovered unchanged.

Action of Lead dioxide and Sulphuric acid on ψ -Meconine.— ψ -Meconine (0.1 g.), water (1 c.c.) and lead dioxide (0.5 g.) were kept at 100° while dilute sulphuric acid was run in. The mixture was heated for an hour, and filtered, when ψ -meconine separated on cooling.

Action of Alkaline Permanganate on ψ -Meconine.—(i) ψ -Meconine (0.2 g.) was dissolved in 2.5% caustic soda solution (10 c.c.) by warming and to the warm solution 1% permanganate solution (11 c.c.) was gradually added and the whole kept for twenty four hours. The whole was warmed up again and filtered and the filtrate acidified. On standing beautiful needles of unchanged ψ -meconine separated. No acid could be isolated from the mother-liquors by extraction with ether etc. (ii) ψ -Meconine (0.1 g.) was dissolved in 2.5 % caustic soda solution (10 c.c.) and to the warm solution was gradually added 1% permanganate (20 c.c.) and the whole warmed up for an hour on the water-bath and kept for twenty four hours. On acidification nothing is precipitated, all the ψ -meconine having been oxidized

away. On extraction with ether a slight amount of an acid, m.p. 180° was obtained, which was found to be hemipinic acid, the rest of the meconine appears to have been completely destroyed. (iii) ψ -Meconine (0.1 g.) was dissolved in 2.5 % caustic soda (10 c.c.) and to the warm solution was gradually added 1% permanganate (10 c.c.) and the whole warmed up for an hour on the water-bath, and kept for twenty four hours, filtered and acidified. On standing part of the ψ -meconine separated out, while the mother-liquor on extraction with ether gave some hemipinic acid. Similar results were obtained when the oxidation was carried out with permanganate in acetone solution.

Bromination of ψ -Meconine.— ψ -Meconine (1.9 g.) was heated in a test tube, fitted up with a reflux-condenser and dropping funnel, to 150° in an oil-bath and dry bromine (.5 c.c.) was gradually added by means of the dropping funnel in bright sunshine in the course of half an hour. Bromination evidently takes place and hydrobromic acid gas was given off. After being allowed to stand over lime, attempts were made without success to crystallise it from the usual organic solvents. It came out as a gum from benzene etc. On trying to crystallise the product from formic acid, a small amount of a crystalline substance melting over 280° was obtained. This substance was insoluble in cold sodium carbonate, but dissolved readily in dilute caustic soda in the cold. It has not yet been found possible to get enough of this substance to characterise it by analysis. But most of the brominated product remained in formic acid solution and did not crystallise on concentration etc. Therefore the product was diluted with water and kept for a few days, when a gum separated, which on boiling with water passed into an acid crystallising in fine needles, m.p. about 200° . This acid contains bromine and forms a compound possibly, an oxime with hydroxylamine.

Some of the freshly brominated product was then examined. It was insoluble in cold sodium carbonate. (i) A little of the crude brominated product was boiled with 25 times its weight of water for a couple of hours and then cooled. The product thus obtained was found to be a mixture. Part of it dissolved in cold sodium carbonate while the undissolved part was found to be a mixture of the unchanged ψ -meconine and brominated product. The part soluble in cold sodium carbonate was thrown down on acidification. In the crude state it melted at about 90° , and was readily soluble in alcohol and only sparingly in water. It did not crystallise in contact with

the usual organic solvents. On boiling with much water part of it dissolved, leaving an undissolved gum. From the aqueous solution an amorphous wooly mass melting at about 200° came down. It contains bromine. (ii) Hydrolysis of the crude brominated product was carried out by boiling for four hours with dilute sodium carbonate solution. Again a similar product to the above was obtained, part of it consisting of an amorphous acid, and part of the unchanged ψ -meconine etc. (iii) Bromination was next carried out at different temperatures viz. at 160° , 170° and 180° , but the brominated products thus obtained did not differ in fundamental characters, from brominated product obtained by the previous method.

Methyl ψ -meconinate. Silver ψ -meconinate (compare Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1890, 57, 1074).— ψ -Meconine (5 g.) was dissolved in barium hydroxide solution (15 g. freshly crystallised in 60 c.c. water) and in the boiling hot solution carbon dioxide was passed till the excess of barium hydroxide was precipitated as barium carbonate. The mixture was then filtered, the filtrate allowed to cool and treated with excess of silver nitrate solution (6 g. in solution). A white curdy precipitate was thrown down. It was kept over-night, filtered, washed with water, methyl alcohol and then ether and allowed to dry in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid. The silver salt was finely powdered, covered with dry ether (150 c.c.) and gently boiled under reflux on a water-bath with excess of methyl iodide (20 c.c.) for 3 hours. After filtering from silver salts, the ethereal solution was concentrated and kept when beautiful prismatic crystals of the ester, m.p. 72° - 73° separated. (Found: C, 58.6; H, 6.1. $C_{11}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 58.4; H, 6.2 per cent.).

Attempts at replacement of the hydroxyl group in the ester by chlorine.—(i) Finely powdered ψ -meconinic ester (1.13 g.) was mixed with dry and pure pyridine (0.4 g.) and to the mixture was gradually added at ordinary temperature (10°), freshly distilled thionyl chloride (0.4 c.c.). Some reaction appeared to take place and ψ -meconinic ester went into solution. On allowing to stand the whole solidified. It was kept for twenty four hours in a test-tube fitted with a calcium chloride tube, the product taken up in a little cold water, filtered and then crystallised from benzene. The crystallised substance melted at 123° - 124° and was identified as ψ -meconine, by the method of mixed melting points. (ii) ψ -Meconinic ester (0.5 g.) was dissolved in dry and redistilled chloroform and to the solution cooled

to 0° was gradually added finely pulverised phosphorous pentachloride (0.6 g.) and the whole allowed to stand for an hour at 0°. The ensuing solution was concentrated in vacuum below 100° and the residue crystallised from benzene when a substance melting at 123°-124° was obtained and was identified as ψ -meconine. (iii) ψ -Meconinic ester (0.2 g.) was dissolved in ether and the ether solution was saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas in presence of sodium sulphate (fused). The whole was kept for 12 hours, filtered, and the ether solution concentrated after being thoroughly washed with water and dried. The concentrated solution deposited on standing crystals of ψ -meconine. (iv) ψ -Meconinic ester (0.2 g.) was treated with a large excess of hydrobromic acid dissolved in glacial acetic acid and the whole kept for 12 hours. Nothing crystallised out, so the whole was diluted with water and extracted with ether, and the ethereal solution dried and concentrated, when ψ -meconine was obtained.

Action of Phosphorous pentachloride on ψ -Meconine.—(i) Phosphorous pentachloride has no action on ψ -meconine at ordinary temperature or when heated on the water-bath for a short time. (ii) Phosphorous pentachloride and ψ -meconine were heated for an hour in an oil-bath at 160°. The product was treated with ice-water and the part insoluble in cold water crystallised from benzene, when unchanged ψ -meconine separated. In another experiment the fresh product was treated with methyl alcohol, but again ψ -meconine was obtained. (iii) At higher temperatures dark uncrystallisable substances were obtained.

Action of hydrobromic acid in glacial acetic acid on ψ -meconine.— ψ -Meconine dissolved in a little glacial acetic acid was treated with a large excess of hydrobromic acid in glacial acetic acid, and the whole kept overnight. No reaction appeared to take place. On dilution unchanged ψ -meconine separated. Action of hydrobromic acid at higher temperatures would be further investigated.

2-Cyan-veratric acid (XVII).—A mixture of 2-amino-veratric acid (7.4 g.), which was prepared by a slight modification of the methods of Pschorr and Sumuleneau (*Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 3408) and of Pisovschi (*Ber.*, 1910, **43**, 2137) from vanillin, water (50 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.), was treated at 0° with sodium nitrite (2.9 g. dissolved in water) and the clear diazo solution was gradually added to a hot solution of potassium-cuprous-cyanide obtained by adding to a solution of coppersulphate

(10 g. in 60 c.c. water) a solution of potassium cyanide (11.2 g. in 20 c.c. water). After the addition of the diazo solution to the cuprous cyanide solution, the mixture was heated for $\frac{1}{4}$ hour on the water-bath, cooled and made slightly acid by means of concentrated hydrochloric acid, when the cyano-acid (XVII) was precipitated. The precipitate was filtered, washed, and dissolved in cold sodium carbonate, filtered from undissolved inorganic substances and the clear solution acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The cyano-acid thus precipitated was collected and crystallised from alcohol with the aid of animal charcoal. It crystallised from alcohol in beautiful long needles, m.p. 208.9.° (Found: C, 58.2; H, 4.5. $C_{10}H_9O_4N$ requires C, 58.0; H, 4.3 per cent.). 2-Cyan-veratric acid is sparingly soluble in ether or chloroform and is readily hydrolysed by boiling with dilute hydrochloric acid to hemipinic acid.

Attempts at conversion of 2-cyan-veratric acid into ψ -opianic acid.—(i) Anhydrous stannous chloride (3 g.), prepared from the pyridine derivative by the method recommended by Stephen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1874) was finely powdered, sieved, suspended in dry ether (20 c.c.) and saturated with dry hydrogen chloride until it had dissolved and the mixture had separated into two layers. 1-Cyan-veratric acid (1 g.) was then added in ether suspension with rapid shaking in a flask fitted with calcium chloride tube. After twelve hours the whole was filtered off and the precipitate heated with water for three hours. After cooling, the aqueous solution was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution concentrated and then extracted three times with sodium carbonate solution. The sodium carbonate solution was concentrated and acidified. An acid m.p. 180° was precipitated, which on recrystallisation from water was obtained in beautiful prismatic needles and was proved to be hemipinic acid. (Found: C, 52.9; H, 4.4. $C_{10}H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 53.1; H, 4.4 per cent.). The hemipinic acid was evidently formed by the hydrolysis of the unchanged 2-cyan-veratric acid. (ii) Finely powdered and sieved anhydrous stannous chloride (3 g.) was suspended in dry ether (20 c.c.) and dry hydrogen chloride was passed into the ether suspension, until it had dissolved and separated in two layers. 2-Cyan-veratric acid (1 g.) dissolved in absolute alcohol was then added with rapid shaking in a flask fitted with a calcium chloride tube. The whole was

allowed to stand for twenty-four hours. No deposition of a double compound took place. The upper ethereal layer on separation and evaporating down gave a substance melting at 228°, which on examination was found to be hemipinimide.

2:3-Dimethoxy-cinnamic acid.—This acid had previously been obtained by condensation of *o*-veratraldehyde with (i) acetic anhydride and sodium acetate at 200° (Heinrich and Krannichfeldt, *Ber.*, 1913, 46, 4021), or (ii) with ethyl acetate in presence of sodium (Perkin and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 103, 2387).

It is obtained in practically quantitative yield by the following method: *o*-Veratraldehyde (100 g.), malonic acid (130 g.), and piperidine (5 c.c.) were heated in pyridine solution (250 c.c.) for 1½ hours on the steam-bath, during which rapid elimination of carbon dioxide took place, and the reaction was completed by boiling for 10 minutes on the sand-bath. The product on pouring into excess of dilute hydrochloric acid gave an almost quantitative yield of 2:3-dimethoxycinnamic acid, m.p. 181°.

Nitration of 2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid in fuming nitric acid.—Well dried 2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid (1 g.) was added in small portions to fuming nitric acid (*d* 1.5, 40 c.c.) cooled in a freezing mixture, the temperature being kept below 0° throughout the reaction. The reaction mixture was poured over ice and water, rubbed, and filtered after a time. The almost colourless precipitate was dried on porous plate and crystallised from alcohol. The nitration product was thus obtained in beautiful colourless prisms, m.p. 198°, which was not elevated on recrystallisation. (Found: N, 9.4. Dinitro-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid, C₁₁H₁₀O₈N₂ requires N, 9.4 per cent.). This substance turned yellow on exposure to the atmosphere.

Nitration with ordinary nitric acid (d 1.42).—(i) Nitration with exactly equivalent amount of nitric acid in glacial acetic acid did not take place at the ordinary temperature. When the nitration in acetic acid was attempted at 90°, indefinite mixtures of the unchanged cinnamic acid and the nitrated compound were obtained. (ii) 2:3-Dimethoxy-cinnamic acid remains unaffected when added to nitric acid cooled to 10°. (iii) Most of the 2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid was nitrated under the following conditions:—2:3-Dimethoxy-cinnamic acid (10 g.), finely powdered and dried was added in small portions to nitric acid (60 c.c.), the whole being stirred vigorously throughout, and the temperature maintained between 10° and 20°.

After a small amount of 2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid had been added, the nitrated product began to separate and in a short time the whole became a semi-solid mass which had to be stirred vigorously by hand or a powerful motor. The mixture was allowed to remain for 3 hours with stirring, and then diluted with a large amount of ice and water, and the precipitated nitro-compounds were filtered, washed and then dried on the steam-bath.

The separation of the nitration product thus obtained was carried out by the following two methods:—(i) The nitration product was repeatedly crystallised from alcohol till an acid melting at 231° was left. The mother-liquors were all mixed together and evaporated down to dryness, and the residue obtained was converted into a mixture of esters by saturating its solution in alcohol (absolute) with dry hydrogen chloride and then boiling it for four hours. The esters thus obtained were separated in the usual manner by careful fractional crystallisations (compare Rubenstein, *loc. cit.*), whereby a less soluble ester, m. p. 116°, was obtained. This crystallises in prisms or prismatic plates. From the more soluble fractions after repeated crystallisation was obtained an ester, m. p. 90°, crystallising in beautiful long needles. For preparation of the acid melting at 231°, which was found to be the 5-nitro-2: 3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid, this method of separation is most convenient. (ii) For effecting a complete separation the following method was found more convenient: The dried mixture of nitro-acids (100 g.), methyl alcohol (600 c.c.), and concentrated sulphuric acid (60 c.c.) were boiled together under reflux for four hours. Methyl alcohol was then removed by distillation, the product diluted with water and neutralised with sodium carbonate, whereby the ester was precipitated. The precipitate was filtered, dried and crystallised from a little alcohol, when the product melted at 128-135°. The whole of the ester obtained (100 g.) was dissolved in a litre of alcohol and allowed to cool, when the crude 5-nitro-2: 3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid separated first. On crystallising this first fraction thrice, 5-nitro-2: 3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid methyl ester was obtained pure as beautiful long needles, m. p. 154-5°. The latter fraction obtained from the mother-liquors was then subjected to a series of careful fractional crystallisations, first from alcohol and then from benzene, whereby an ester, m. p. 150°, was obtained, which was found to be methyl 6-nitro-2: 3-dimethoxy-cinnamate crystallising in colourless beautiful long needles. A mixture of the two esters melted about 130°.

The ethyl ester, m. p. 116° and the methyl ester, m. p. 154.5° gave on hydrolysis an acid melting at 231° , which was identical with 5-nitro-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid obtained by synthesis, and the two esters were also identical, as shown by mixed melting points, with the corresponding esters prepared from the synthetical 5-nitro-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid.

The ethyl ester m. p. 90° and the methyl ester m. p. 150° gave on hydrolysis an acid m. p. 220° , which was identical with 6-nitro-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid, and are therefore the ethyl and methyl esters of 6-nitro-2:3-dimethoxy cinnamic acid. (Found for ethyl ester m. p. 90° : N, 4.9. $C_{13}H_{15}O_6N$ requires N, 5.0 per cent. Found for methyl ester m. p. 150° : N, 5.3. $C_{12}H_{13}O_6N$ requires N, 5.2 per cent.).

6-Nitro-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid (XVIII.)—(i) 6-Nitro-2:3-dimethoxy-benzaldehyde (10 g.), malonic acid (11 g.) and piperidine (5 c.c.) were heated in pyridine solution (25 c.c.) for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours on the steam-bath during which period some elimination of carbon dioxide took place and the liquid turned dark, and then the whole was boiled for a further period of ten minutes. The product on pouring into excess of dilute hydrochloric acid gave a dark mass. After filtration and examination, the dark product proved to be a mixture of two substances, one of which was insoluble in cold sodium carbonate while the other was not. The soluble part was precipitated by acid and crystallised from alcohol with the aid of animal charcoal. It crystallised in colourless needles m. p. 220° and is obviously 6-nitro-2:3-dimethoxy cinnamic acid. The part that was insoluble in sodium carbonate was a brown amorphous substance, almost insoluble in methyl or ethyl alcohol. It could not be obtained so far in a crystalline state. (ii) Most of the 6-nitro-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid required for the following experiments was obtained by the hydrolysis of the ester obtained from the mixture of esters of the nitro-compounds obtained by direct nitration of 2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid as already described. The hydrolysis of the ester is best effected under the following conditions:—

The pure ester (2 g.) was taken up in water (10 c.c.) and to the mixture was added all at once concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) and the whole shaken vigorously. The ester went into solution (colourless), and the hydrolysis was practically complete in a minute, but still to ensure completion, glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) was added and the mixture boiled for 5 minutes, during which the nitro-acid began to separate. The reaction product was poured over ice,

allowed to remain for sometime, filtered, washed, dried, and crystallised from alcohol. It crystallises in colourless needles and melts sharply at 220° (compare Rubenstein who described it as a brown substance of m. p. $210-215^{\circ}$, *loc. cit.*). (Found: N, 5.6. $C_{11}H_{11}O_6N$ requires N, 5.5 per cent.). This acid gave the same mixed melting point with the acid obtained by the method (i). To obtain further evidence for the constitution of this acid, the acid was oxidized to 6-nitro-2:3-dimethoxy-benzaldehyde under the following conditions:—6-Nitro-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid (0.5 g.) was suspended in water (20 c.c.) and a little sodium carbonate solution (2 c.c.) added and stirred when the nitro-cinnamic acid went in solution. The solution was taken up in a separating funnel mixed with benzene (50 c.c.) and to the mixture was gradually added a cold saturated solution of potassium permanganate (0.7 g. in 11.7 c.c. water). After each addition of permanganate the mixture was vigorously shaken and cooled under the tap. After the addition of all the permanganate the mixture was allowed to remain for a few minutes and then filtered. The precipitate of manganese dioxide was washed with benzene, the benzene layer separated from the aqueous layer, dried over sodium sulphate, and the solvent removed by distillation when an almost colourless residue (0.25 g.) was left. On crystallisation from methyl alcohol or benzene it melted at 110° and a mixed melting point with 6-nitro-2:3-dimethoxy-benzaldehyde caused no depression.

6-Amino-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid (XIX).—To a solution of ferrous sulphate (recrystallised, 16 g.) in water (30 c.c.) heated up to 90° was added a solution of 6-nitro-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid (2 g.) in dilute ammonia. To the mixture heated on the water-bath was then gradually added concentrated ammonia (6 c.c.), while the contents were vigorously shaken throughout. After the addition of ammonia the whole was heated for a further $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, filtered, the filtrate concentrated down to one third its volume, and then carefully made just acid. The amino-acid was precipitated as a crystalline yellow powder. It was recrystallised from boiling water when it was obtained as glistening prisms, m.p. 179° . (Found: N, 6.4. $C_{11}H_{13}O_4N$ requires N, 6.3 per cent.). In contact with hydrochloric acid it readily passes into the hydrochloride. Both the amino acid and its hydrochloride are much more soluble in the usual solvents than its isomer, 5-amino-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid and its hydrochloride,

6-Cyano-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid (XX).—A mixture of 6-amino-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid (2.2 g.), water (11 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (2.3 c.c.) was treated at 0° with sodium nitrite (0.75 g.) and the clear diazo solution filtered from a trace of insoluble substance and was added to a hot solution of potassium-cuprous-cyanide, obtained by adding to a solution of copper sulphate (2.5 g. in 15 c.c.) a solution of potassium cyanide (2.8 g. in 5 c.c. water). After the addition of the diazo solution to the potassium cuprous cyanide solution, the mixture was heated for a further quarter of an hour on the water-bath, cooled and made slightly acid by means of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The cyano acid was precipitated. The precipitate was filtered, washed, extracted or shaken up with cold sodium carbonate solution, filtered from a slight amount of undissolved inorganic substance and the clear solution acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The cyano acid thus obtained was collected and crystallised from alcohol with the aid of animal charcoal. It crystallised from alcohol in glistening needles, m.p. 238°. (Found: C, 62.1; H, 4.8. $C_{12}H_{11}NO_4$ requires C 61.8; H, 4.7 per cent.).

Attempts at oxidation of 6-Cyano-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid to 6-Cyano-2:3-dimethoxy-benzaldehyde.—(i) 6-Cyano-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid (1 g.) was suspended in water (40 c.c.) and a little sodium carbonate solution (5 c.c.) added and stirred when cyano-cinnamic acid went in solution. The solution was taken up in a separating funnel, mixed with benzene (100 c.c.) and to the mixture was gradually added a saturated solution of potassium permanganate (1.4 g. in 23.4 c.c.). After each addition of permanganate the mixture was vigorously shaken and cooled under the tap. After the addition of all the permanganate, the mixture was allowed to remain for a few minutes and then filtered. The precipitate of manganese dioxide was washed with benzene. The benzene layer, separated from the aqueous-layer (A), was dried over sodium sulphate and the solvent removed, when a colourless residue (0.1 g.) remained. When crystallised from water it came out as needles which turned yellow on exposure to air and light. It shrinks at about 115° and melts completely at about 220°. (Found: C, 53.8; H, 4.2. $C_{10}H_9O_3N$ requires C, 62.8; H, 4.7 per cent.). When crystallized from benzene it came out as a crystalline powder, m.p. about 225°. (Found: N, 7.0 per cent.). (ii) The oxidation was next carried out below 0° under conditions essentially similar to the above, but

slight excess of permanganate (1.8 g.) being used. The same product was again obtained. This substance was not hydrolysed to any acid by boiling for four hours with the following hydrolysing agents:— (1) dilute hydrochloric acid, (2) concentrated hydrochloric acid in ethereal solution, (3) 20 per cent. sulphuric acid. It was converted into tarry substances by boiling with a mixture of equal volumes of water, sulphuric acid and glacial acetic acid or by warming with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The substance was also decomposed by boiling with dilute alkali. (iii) Attempts to oxidize the cyano-cinnamic-acid to the corresponding cyano-aldehyde by means of alkaline hydrogen peroxide were also unsuccessful.

The aqueous filtrate (A) obtained in (i) and (ii) on acidification, did not give any precipitate, so the acidified solution was extracted several times with ether, which however extracted nothing. The aqueous solution was therefore neutralised, and concentrated down and then acidified. Nothing crystallisable was precipitated. In another experiment, the aqueous filtrate (A) was carefully neutralised. The neutral solution does not give any precipitate with barium chloride, lead acetate or silver nitrate.

6-Carboxy-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid (XXIII).—6-Cyan-2:3-dimethoxy cinnamic acid (0.5 g.) was boiled for two hours with 10 per cent. sodium hydroxide solution (10 c.c.), cooled and carefully acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid and kept for twenty-four hours. The crystalline precipitate was collected and crystallised from water with the aid of animal charcoal. It crystallised in beautiful needles, m.p. 194°, and is readily soluble in hot water and alcohol but rather sparingly in ether. (Found: C, 57.3; H, 4.9. $C_{12}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 57.1; H, 4.8 per cent.).

Oxidation of the carboxy-cinnamic acid.—(i) 6-Carboxy-2:3-dimethoxy-cinnamic acid (1 g.) was dissolved in a little dilute sodium carbonate solution and diluted to 40 c.c. A saturated solution of permanganate (1.5 g. in 25 c.c. water) was added very slowly to the solution which was kept below 0° and continually stirred. After remaining for 12 hours, the whole was filtered and acidified when a crystalline precipitate gradually appeared. It crystallised from alcohol in beautiful long needles, m.p. 202°. (Found: C, 55.79, 55.85; H, 4.84, 4.75 per cent.). This substance does not form an oxime and has none of the properties of ψ -opianic acid. The filtrate from the above precipitate was extracted with ether, the ether solution dried, and the ether removed when it was found that ether had

extracted nothing. The filtrate was therefore concentrated down, but nothing definitely crystallisable was obtained. (ii) A similar product was obtained when oxidation was carried out with 2 per cent. potassium permanganate solution.

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